

Participatory mapping workshop: How do STS and Citizen Science interact?

Christian Nold & Emma Garnett & all of you

We will map the intersection of STS and Citizen Science by analysing the practices of Citizen Science, in terms of what is produced and affecting the world. Our workshop uses Adele Clarke's Situational Mapping (2003) where the research situation is the unit of analysis. Situational mapping generates visual representations. Today we are going to do this mapping collectively to visualise the multiple practices, spaces, and possibilities of STS and Citizen Science.

We are trying to do this via 3 drawing activities

We hope you will join us in this collaborate research. We will create a shared document with all the drawings as well as notes from the workshop. As a co-author, please contribute to writing and editing these notes. We are building on a similar workshop at ECSA2024 in Vienna, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12522890> - see below for the list of authors. By taking part in this workshop you agree to be a named co-author on the workshop report that we will place in a public repository licenced under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0. Please email us if you do not want to be included as a co-author.

Your name:

Your email:

References:

Clarke, Adele E. 2003. "Situational Analyses: Grounded Theory Mapping After the Postmodern Turn." *Symbolic Interaction* 26 (4): 553–76. <https://doi.org/10.1525/si.2003.26.4.553>.

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Activity 1 Draw your practice

We want to capture what STS people do when they are in contact with Citizen Science. Please try and include yourself in the drawing. ***What do you do when in contact with Citizen Science?*** What instruments and objects do you use? There are two additional boxes if you have multiple practices or wish to show details. You can use words to give context if it helps.

Activity 2 Draw a map of a Citizen Science project

Draw a mental map/diagram of a Citizen Science project that you have been involved with. If you have worked with many, just pick a specific one. **What are the sites, spaces and places where the project took place?** Where was the project planned, 'made' and analysed? Finally, add yourself to show at what points you were involved.

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for the student to draw a mental map or diagram of a Citizen Science project. The box occupies most of the page's width and height.

Map Legend
(if you want)

Activity 3 Expand the map of the project

Expand the map/diagram you drew on the previous page. ***What was produced and changed in the world as a result of the project?*** Try to be as specific and concrete as you can. If you are not sure, or there is a ambiguity or a disconnect, draw that uncertainty. If you were involved in this expansion then add yourself to the map.

Imagine your
previous map
here

Map Legend
(if you want)